

Research on Motivation Model of Talented Employees Between China and Thailand

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Abstract

Understanding the basis of literature review about talent management and motivation, and in the part of analysis of talented employees, the factors effects the motivation of talented employees and establishing the model are firstly analysed and described clearly. The basic understanding condition of organizations in China and Thailand are then elaborated. Next, questionnaires are designed and distributed in both countries. The returned questionnaires were collected for further analysis using SPSS. Analysis shows conclusions that motivation's factors affect most on Thailand or China At last, some suggestions to improve motivation of talented employees in both countries are given.

Keywords: Motivation; Talented Employees; Human Resource; Talent Management; Motivation factors.

1. Introduction

In the past, machinery, investment and location are competitive advantage. But in presents, when the competition into era of the knowledge economy, a leading organization is paying attention to the employees in the organization as a factor of the success of the organization (Thitiporn Chomphukam, 2004, p.1), as "the chief executive of Honeywell has expressed confidence that in the end, we had a bet in the business by man, not a strategy" (Chambers, Handfield-Jones, Hankin, & Michaels III, 1998), consistent with the theory of human capital (Becker 1964, referred to Somboon Kunwisetchana, 2006, p.12) which says knowledge, ability and potential of human when It has been developed more, it also affect the value of the organization more. Talented employees became a key success factor of business. It is an important in the organization by the beginning of the success in the organization is to put people to suit the time and location to achieve the maximum benefit for the organization. And for this cause the success result it needs the organizational skills for human resource management creatively and intelligently, in order to pull the potential and ability that exists in the workforce to achieve maximum benefit. The changes that occur over time in terms of technology, education, practical process along with all the law which causes the organization must adjust plans that focus on all aspects of human resource management, workforce planning, recruiting, developing and retaining the quality management. Payment of compensation and benefits are including the evaluation for the success of the organization (Prapaiwan Summatitthi, 2009). One important factor that pushes the employees to work or to do something success, it start from "Motivation". We can see that some practitioners who work or do some activity are very energetic, lively, concentrated, conscientious, etc. But while some practitioners do not work or do not want to do through the day in the state, sluggish, gloomy and does not care whether the job will be good or bad, but somehow different behavior these occur as a result of the motivation of the individual.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Talented Employees and Talent Management

Talented employees is a person who has a good potential, knowledge, abilities, skills, creativity, curiosity, enthusiasm, needs to progress, leadership, communication skills and ability to motivate others, have an ability to

solve the problems, including they have a purpose of work to achieve the goal of the organizations clearly. Thus, talented employees who have the high performance and high potential are distinguished from other personnel.

So that, Talent Management is very important to the development organization to the goal, it is the administrative one that tries to be used to benefit. (Krittpong dechsongjarad, 2012) if the organization can manage talented employees, it will be organization capability and has the competitive advantage by talent management. Organization must be analyzed in a systematic and planned in line with the organization's mission, policies and cultural with context and appropriateness of the organization. In another expression, it can be said that talent management encompasses almost all the elements of human resource management (Stewart. & Harte, 2010).

2.2 Understanding Motivation Model and Theories

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory (Maslow, 1954) was a psychologist of humanism. His theory is a theory called Hierarchy of Needs explained that there needs to be sequenced. It was found that individuals often struggling to meet the minimum requirements before upon receiving the response. Then, they seek to the next step. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory have 7 step as follow; Physical Needs, Safety Needs, Belongingness and Love Needs, Esteem Needs, Need to Know and Understand, Aesthetic Needs, Self-Actualization Needs respectively.

ERG Theory (Existence Relatedness Growth Theory) is Clayton Alderfer's theory; it is based on the hierarchy of needs theory from Maslow. It has to offer about basic 3 needs first is Existence needs, second is Relatedness Needs and third is Growth Needs.

Herzberg 2 Factors Theory (Frederick Herzberg, 1959) is a psychologist who committed another study about the motivation to work. His work has appeared widely on this issue since 1966. And 1968 the problems that he kept asking himself is how to motivate people to work very well, he saw that the workers did not satisfied with low-wage, and the high wages also did not make the workers want to work harder. The money is not the maximum motivator to make the employees hard work or complete the job more than ever, although money is important. Meanwhile, security and good atmosphere in the organization, it is not the highest motivator as well. Herzberg's theory emphasis and focus on the factors described two aspects "Motivators and "Hygiene", these two factors influence the success of the work. That is the executive of organization should be considered in order to take advantage of human management and administration.

J. Stacy Adams (1965) who was developed this theory. The basic idea is that a person shall seek social equality by consider the reward should be received (output) and (Input) is the behavior and properties in which he put to work for equality. It based on the comparison of perceived Inputs to Outputs when we know the efficacy of any person equality. Then, we were able to predict the performance of his work. Expectancy Theory is the theory Victor Vroom which is described by the formula. [Motivation = Expectancy x Valence]

It implies that the motivation is based on the needs of the people that they have on any one thing and the possibility that they will get it.

3. Research Method

3.1 Establishing Motivation Model of Talented Employees

In this motivation model have 11 factors, it has been adapted to be used for this research. It is classified into 2 conditions follow the figure below.

Figure 1: Implementation the Motivation Model

11 factors mentioned above, it will be used in the questionnaire for survey in both countries. They have been separate into 44 questions, explained in each factor as follow;

1. Work achievement is the person can work and it completed successfully. That person must understand and know what they should do; put in order step by step, the ability to work within a designated time to succeed with quality and performance can be seen clearly.
2. Respectability is the person has been respected by colleagues, leaders or from any other groups. It's about how you behave and attitude toward others. So whether who are you, which generation you are; and what occupation are you; you are entitled to the respect of others as well. It is ridiculous that many people seeking acceptance from others but they never regards themselves even less. If you are not care for yourselves, then do not hope that someone else will come in you. Therefore, you should start by loving yourself first then, you will get a love and interest from others in the future.
3. Quality of work is quality of work or duty that have been assigned to perform which encourage creativity and ambitious of each person's ability. Personal feelings toward the nature of the job sometimes talent employees also need to pay attention and be aware of them. This could be seen from work that has been assigned to perform, it is diverse, interesting and important to the organization more or less. And they are free to perform and urged the chance to work on their own decisions.
4. Responsibility is satisfaction arising when employee has been tasked with the responsibility of new jobs and competent full responsibility and abilities fully operational. Or even admit their mistakes and they are ready to fix their mistakes too.
5. Promotion is changing in the status or position of the people in the organization. Also refers to situations where a person can get progressively developing knowledge and skills from their job. Or even self-development training, seminar and include the opportunity to study at a higher level which supported by the company towards its employees. This is the good way to build an opportunity as a benefit in exchange

for loyalty between employees toward company. Currently, most companies have been operating in this manner as well.

6. Policy and Development is the organization or company have clearly policies and management that everybody can be practical and acceptable in common. For working with large groups of people should manage in the systematic, step by step, planning to perform well and the decentralization of operations. For all sectors and all the people should have been worked by their ability to engage in that work. This is an important part of working to make it faster, smooth and truly effective.
7. Administration and Command is the ability of the supervisor to operate or parities in the administration of justice, and to control their subordinates in an order with a good tradition. Supervisors should have the foresight, be steady and calm for resolve the problems.
8. Relationship between individual is the contact or verbal behavior that represents a good relationship with each other. Whether, it is with subordinates or colleagues. On a basic level of intimacy between the leader and their man is important, it reduces the gap between them. At times, the organization has a great friendly atmosphere; it creates unity, cooperation in working as one. The result was not only a success in the task. But also the organization was able to move forward as well.
9. Work condition is a condition and good atmosphere for everyone's happiness in the workplace. Materials and tools are fully. Facilities are ready for operation, or the environment and the atmosphere in the workplace are clear. There is a proportion that is conducive to the operation. The placement of articles arranges in the proper way and easy to apply.
10. Stability is a person with a sense of job security and stability in the organization. This may be considering the work that has been entrusted to the ongoing practice. Or the employees themselves have confidence in the organization or in a profession that do exist. Or even that the company is known, it demonstrates the strength of the company with a positive outlook, that the stability of our job and position are following the same direction of the organization as well.
11. Salary is another means of subsistence which is an important of motivation for employees. The salary will provide to employees by the organizations consider the suitability of performance of the individual. And the benefits for employees has become the driving force for employees to work more fully also.

4. The Results of this Research

4.1. Data Analysis Method

For this research, IBM SPSS Statistics 21 becomes our method for statistical analysis data. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences or SPSS after being developed by Norman H. Nie, Dale H. Bent, and C. Hadlai Hull. Those principals incorporated as SPSS Inc. in 1975^[12]. It was acquired by IBM in 2009. SPSS is a widely used program for statistical analysis in social science. It is also used by market researchers, health researchers, survey companies, government, education researchers, marketing organizations, data miners, and others.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics for China and Thailand

From this survey, we managed the questionnaires total 400 sets. By we distribute 200 sets per country. This survey is managed by online and the questionnaire form. 158 sets feedbacks are collected after about 3 months of whole survey process which respondent are employees in Thailand. And For China this survey is only in questionnaire form. Total 168 sets feedbacks. It was mainly from of 20 companies in Jiangsu, Shanghai and other places. The results we present into 2 parts. The first part is comparison general information of respondents between both countries and in the second part will compare in sub-factor from each questions that the results we received it shows that;

1. Gender

64 and 94 of 158 respondents are male and female, respectively, standing 40.5% and 59.5%. Female respondents tend to be more willing and voluntary to help compared to male. This number also can reflect the fact that the female population in Thailand more than male. Compared to China 26 and 142 of 168 respondents are male and female, respectively, accounting 15.5% and 84.5%. The survey in Thailand ratio is balanced between genders more than in China. Although in China have more population than Thailand.

2. Age

Nearly 62% of Thailand respondents are less than 31 years old. Also, most of Chinese respondents are less than 31 years old as same as Thai's respondents. This might become the limit of this research due to the lack of representativeness.

3. Education

Thailand respondents which are the level of undergraduate have made the survey 71.5% of all among other degrees. But the highest of Chinese respondents are postgraduate 81%.

4. Job Sector

For China and Thailand 97% and 92.4% respectively Most of respondents from China and Thailand are private officer. It shows that this survey may not have access to all parts. Because in the part of the government to carry out, If not specified and plot the area that need to collect data manually one by one, it is very difficult to access.

5. Work Experience

For Thailand less than 6 years of work experience at 63.3%, next is 6-10 years at 19%, 11-15 years at 7%, more than 20 years at 8.9% and 16-20 years at 1.9%. 42.9% of Chinese respondents are frequent work experience less than 6 years. This number is less than compared to Thailand ones. But 6-10 years 39.9% is higher than Thailand. In this part it proves that it is reasonable between work experience and education.

6. Position

For this part of position have variety. According to the survey form in other 57.6% is the highest that the Thailand respondents are work in the different field such as CEO, reporter, consultant, manager, etc. And 62.5% for Chinese respondents are work at human resources position.

Table1: New Model of Motivation Factors between China and Thailand

China	Thailand
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Work Achievement ● Responsibility ● Respectability ● Policy and Development ● Promotion ● Relationship between Individual ● Stability ● Work Condition ● Quality of Work ● Administration and Command ● Salary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Responsibility ● Stability ● Quality of Work ● Work Achievement ● Respectability ● Relationship between Individual ● Administration and Command ● Work Condition ● Promotion ● Policy and Development ● Salary

we can distribute from the highest to the lowest as the new model among all the 11 factors, we can see that the highest motivation factor for Chinese employees focus on is work achievement in the part of achieve the assigned task and for Thailand the highest motivation factor is responsibility in the part of improving when they make mistakes. It is show that from their own culture and behavior of employees in each country.

Chinese employees focus on work achievement can describe the reason into 2 points. Firstly, Chinese people are rather industrious and be a fighter to life. Almost work every day and go back home late at night because they think every minute costly. People build a country; they were cultivated from predecessor it may be said that it is in the blood vain of them that it is. These reflect what we have seen the richness, strength and stable of China until this day.

Secondly, Chinese people really work hard and diligent because if works out well, It can guarantee stability in their career. And it will affect the future that will not be fired, because they have a good performance and behavior at work. And may include receive special prizes or bonus at the end of year.

For Thailand employees which focus on responsibility, if we say about the responsibility of Thai people; they were instilled in people a long term; both in home and classroom lessons. Thai people were to raise awareness that people need to take responsibility for their own national, society, and the people around them. And they were influenced by

Buddhism that it is a national religion, to realize what is right what is wrong as a perception. The conclusions that came out with the characterization of Thai people, it is no wonder that most employees will accept the false and self-improvement as a rank one. Although this result is opposite direction from the society in this presents but it shows that among all of them, most of people still perform well.

5. Conclusion

The weakness of both countries is factor of salary. The result is same. It shows that today, we would not deny that "money" is important in life. The people are dedicated to work for the organization; of course they expect to be paid a proper compensation. And in many cases, the decision to work with this or that company is always attention at the money or compensation of the work for all. But when we walk into the organization, it will show that we have chosen to work in, which offers compensation and benefits suit for us right now. But what makes us feel dedicated to building a portfolio and wanted to stay with the organization in the long term. Most depend on other factors such as growth in their career path, work-life balance, or environment etc. All the factors mentioned above. It is seen that the money is only part of the staff that is able to attract good people to work with the organization, but the organization will motivate employees dedicated or keeping them with the organization for a long time. Money cannot be done If your organization to focus on the growth path or work-life balance, as well as the environment. Many of these are reflected that in the management or organization with a focus on employees. And employees will feel good for the organization and they want to stay with the organization in long term.

We can see that as mentioned above all can conclude that both employees from China and Thailand are similar in intrinsic motivation. They will loyalty to the organization and in such conditions it is seen that many employees who is not leave the organization and willing to work during holidays without compensation. If such action is to go by the feeling or a good attitude to owner or responsibilities as a member of the organization, not for fear of being fired or fear of do not have a place to go.

References

- [1] Thitiporn Chomphukam 2004, "Talent Management"; A significant Tool for Significant Persons [J]. Journal of Chulalongkorn Business Review, 2004, vol. 26 (101), pp. 1.
- [2] Elizabeth G. Chambers, Mark Foulon, Helen Handfield-Jones, Steven M. Hankin, and Edward G. Michaels III, "The war for talent" [J], The McKinsey Quarterly: The Online Journal of McKinsey & Co., pp. 1-8.
- [3] Somboon Kunwisetchana, Retaining talent people [J], Journal of business management, vol. 29 (109) pp.12, 2006.
- [4] Prapaiwan Summatithi, 2009. Talent Management: A Case of Standard charters Bank (Thailand) [J]. Bangkok: Faculty of Political Science, Thammasat University, 2009, vol. 70: pp.15-17.
- [5] Krittipong Dechsongjarad, Talent Management Chapter 8: Replaces the talent management [M]. Bangkok: Chulalongkorn University press, 2012.
- [6] Stewart, J. and V. Harte, The implication of talent management for diversity training: an exploratory study [J]. Journal of European Industrial Training, 2010, vol. 34(6), pp. 506-518.
- [7] Maslow, Abraham M. Motivation and Personality [M]. New York: Harper and Row, 1954.
- [8] Alderfer, Clayton P. Existence Relatedness and Growth [M]. New York: Free Press, 1972.
- [9] Herzberg F. The Motivation of Work [M]. New York: John Wiley & Sons, 1959.
- [10] Adams, J.S. Inequality in Social Exchange in Advances in Experimental Psychology [A], L. Berkowitz (ed.) [C], Academic Press, New York, NY. Vol.2, pp. 267-299, 1965
- [11] Victor H. Vroom, Work and Motivation [M], New York: Wiley, 1964.
- [12] Norman H. Nie, Dale H. Bent, and C. Hadlai Hull. SPSS: statistical package for the social sciences 2nd ed. [M], New York: McGraw-Hill.Inc., 1975.

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